

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: Q-PLAN

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101000788.

"Let's meet!" Event Validation Report - Greece

Issued by: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL
Issue date: 15/03/2023
Due date: 30/04/2023
Work Package Leader: MTU (Task Leader: Q-PLAN)

Start date of project: 01 January 2021

Duration: 36 months

Document History

Version	Date	Changes
1.0	15/03/2023	Draft version
2.0	28/03/2023	Final version

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of **Q-PLAN** for the organisation and validation of the **Open Day** event organised **at the American Farm School in Thessaloniki, Greece on March 11th, 2023**. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Open Day event at the American Farm School.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

The **Open Day event** concept was chosen in Greece, organised in collaboration with the **American Farm School (AFS)**, an educational institution in Thessaloniki that offers educational programmes spanning all grades from pre-school to Masters’ degrees. The American Farm school also has a large farm that produces, as part of its educational activities, various products that are sold in the local market. The event took place on Saturday, 11th of March between 11:00 – 15:00 (local time) at the premises of the American Farm School.

During the event, members of the public and their families were offered a tour at the premises and educational farm of the American Farm School to learn about the farm’s activities and products, concluded with lunch made using the products of the school.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Registration and welcome	Arrival and registration of attendees, distribution of programme and feedback forms. Offered coffee, refreshments and snacks made with AFS products.	11:00 – 11:30	Perrotis College Lobby, American Farm School
Presentations	Presentation of the agroBRIDGES project and of the American Farm School mission and activities.	11.30 – 12.00	Perrotis College Auditorium, American Farm School
Walking tour	Tour of the school premises and the educational farm, including the dairy unit, the vegetable farm plots, and the campus store.	12.00 – 13.00	American Farm School
Lunch	Lunch at the campus restaurant in the form of buffet offering local dishes, most of which were made with AFS products.	13.00 – 14.00	Perrotis College Restaurant, American Farm School

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The event was held at the American Farm School campus, in Thermi, Thessaloniki, which is located approximately 15-20 minutes driving distance east of the city center. The American Farm School opened their campus and educational farm for the event participants and engaged personnel for the presentation of AFS activities, for venue and equipment set up, the walking tour, the provision of catering services as well as a

professional photographer to develop a video about the event. Moreover, the promotion of the event was supported by the school. The maximum participation of the event was agreed to be circa 50 persons.

Three indoor spaces at the “**Aliki Perroti**” Student Residence & Cafeteria building were used to cater for the event needs: (i) **lobby** for coffee, snacks and reception, (ii) **auditorium** for the presentations, (iii) **cafeteria / restaurant** for lunch, after the end of the walking tour.

Q-PLAN contacted the **HUB for Innovation and Impact** of the American Farm School 3.5 months in advance, to organise a meeting with the event planning team to agree on the scope of activities, logistics, costs and the event date. An internal memo was used to build a common understanding between the teams and discuss next steps. When full agreement was reached, one month before the event, Q-PLAN and the American Farm School signed an agreement. A few days before the event, the team of Q-PLAN visited the premises of the school to plan final details.

The images below show how the indoor spaces were set up for the Open Day event.

Figure 1: Lobby area – Attendees’ reception and registration

Figure 2: Restaurant area

Figure 3: Auditorium

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation / Activity	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Event planning	4	Logistics and activities' organisation	In-house / External (AFS)	6 - 8
Preparation of presentations	1	Preparation of presentation material (agroBRIDGES)	In-house	0.1
Graphic design	1	Adaptation of promotional material and development of registration forms	1 in-house	1
Event promotion	> 4	Participants' reception and registration, speakers, walking tour guides.	In-house (3 Q-PLAN / >1 AFS)	0.5
Event delivery	8	Speakers / presenters, walking tour guides, participants' reception, IT equipment set-up.	In-house (2 Q-PLAN / 6 AFS)	2 – 2.5
Catering	>3	Preparation and serving snacks and meals, for breakfast and lunch.	External	N/A
Photography	1	Photography and video recording of the event, production of professional video.	External	N/A

2.4 Event material

To organise the Open Day event, the templates of the “Let’s meet!” tool were used, adapted to the scope and activities of the event. The language used for all material and communications was Greek. The following materials were prepared to promote, carry out and report event activities: (i) Event invitation, (ii) Event programme, (iii) Social media graphic for event announcement, (iv) List of participants, (iv) Registration form, (v) Feedback form.

The event evaluation form was modelled after the template that has been developed for the Open Day concept, provided in the Event Validation Guidelines of Task 4.3. The developed materials are illustrated in the following figures.

Figure 4: Event templates and promotional material in Greek

Event programme

Invitation

Participants' list

Figure 5: Online registration form in Greek (event information and consent provision)

Section 1 of 3

Φόρμα Εγγραφής στην Εκδήλωση «Επίσκεψη σε Αγρόκτημα – Open Day»

Διοργανωτής: Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL, σε συνεργασία με την ΑΜΕΡΙΚΑΝΙΚΗ ΓΕΩΡΓΙΚΗ ΣΧΟΛΗ Θεσσαλονίκης

Ημερομηνία Εκδήλωσης: Σάββατο, 11 Μαρτίου 2023

Ώρα Εκδήλωσης: 11:00 – 14:00

Διεύθυνση Εκδήλωσης: ΑΜΕΡΙΚΑΝΙΚΗ ΓΕΩΡΓΙΚΗ ΣΧΟΛΗ Θεσσαλονίκης, Μαρίνου Αντύπα 54, Θέρμη Θεσσαλονίκης

Πρόγραμμα Εκδήλωσης

Επικοινωνία: efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr; malliopoulos@qplan-intl.gr

Η εκδήλωση αυτή διοργανώνεται στο πλαίσιο του έργου [agroBRIDGES](#), που έλαβε χρηματοδότηση από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας «Horizon 2020» της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης με Συμφωνία Επιχορήγησης Αρ. 101000788.

Παρακαλούμε διαβάστε προσεκτικά την [Πολιτική Αποφασίτου](#) του έργου και το [Έντυπο Ευνοησόμενης Συγκατάθεσης](#) που παρέχει πληροφορίες σχετικά με τη χρήση και την προστασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων για την εκδήλωση αυτή.

Email *

Valid email

This form is collecting emails. [Change settings](#)

Section 2 of 3

Συγκατάθεση

Παρακαλούμε διαβάστε προσεκτικά την [Πολιτική Αποφασίτου](#) του έργου και το [Έντυπο Ευνοησόμενης Συγκατάθεσης](#) που παρέχει πληροφορίες σχετικά με τη χρήση και την προστασία των προσωπικών σας δεδομένων για την εκδήλωση αυτή.

Δηλώνω ότι δίνω τη συγκατάθεσή μου για την επεξεργασία των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων που απαιτούνται για:

Description (optional)

Τη συμμετοχή μου στην τοπική εκδήλωση της Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL που θα υλοποιηθεί από το έργο agroBRIDGES στους χώρους της Αμερικανικής Γεωργικής Σχολής στη Θέρμη Θεσσαλονίκης καθώς και την παροχή σχολίων μου για την εκδήλωση με στόχο τη βελτίωση της στο μέλλον.

(Εάν δεν δώσετε τη συγκατάθεσή σας για αυτόν τον σκοπό, η εγγραφή σας δεν θα είναι έγκυρη. Εάν δεν συναινείτε, σταματήστε τη διαδικασία εγγραφής.)

Ναι

Τη συμμετοχή μου σε μελλοντικές δράσεις του έργου agroBRIDGES.

Ναι

Όχι

Τη λήψη ενημερωτικών μηνυμάτων ή δελτίων σχετικά με τις δράσεις του έργου agroBRIDGES.

Ναι

Όχι

Figure 6: Online registration form in Greek (participant demographics)

Section 3 of 3

Εγγραφή ✕ ⋮

Description (optional)

Όνομα *

Short answer text

Επώνυμο *

Short answer text

Φύλο *

Γυναίκα

Άνδρας

Άλλο

Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

Επωνυμία οργανισμού

Short answer text

Παρακαλώ επιλέξτε την περιγραφή που ταιριάζει καλύτερα σε σας ή τον οργανισμό σας. *

Αγρότες ή/και άλλοι παραγωγοί

Καταναλωτές και λάτρεις της καλής διατροφής

Υπεύθυνοι χάραξης πολιτικής, οργανισμοί πολιτικής ή δημόσιοι φορείς

Εκπαιδευτές, εκπαιδευτικοί και εκπαιδευτικοί οργανισμοί (σχολεία, πανεπιστήμια κλπ.)

Πάροχοι τεχνολογίας

Ομάδες, δίκτυα και άλλοι οργανισμοί υποστήριξης επιχειρήσεων αγρο-διατροφής

Ενώσεις Παραγωγών

Ενώσεις Καταναλωτών

Τύπος και Μέσα Μαζικής Επικοινωνίας

Other...

Figure 7: Event evaluation form in Greek

Ερωτηματολόγιο Αξιολόγησης Εκδήλωσης agroBRIDGES

«Open Day – Επίσκεψη στο αγρόκτημα της Αμερικανικής Γεωργικής Σχολής»

Ερώτηση #1: Ήσασταν εξοικειωμένος/εξοικειωμένη με την έννοια των Βραχέων Εφοδιαστικών Αλυσίδων Προϊόντων Διατροφής πριν από αυτήν την εκδήλωση;

Ναι

Όχι

Δεν είμαι σίγουρος/σίγουρη

Ερώτηση #2: Βρήκατε την εκδήλωση ενημερωτική για νέα/άγνωστα προϊόντα διατροφής που παράγονται στην περιοχή σας;

Πολύ ενημερωτική

Αρκετά ενημερωτική

Ουδέτερη

Όχι πολύ ενημερωτική

Καθόλου ενημερωτική

Ερώτηση #3: Βρήκατε αυτή τη δραστηριότητα χρήσιμη για να γνωρίσετε τον παραγωγό/την επιχείρηση που επισκεφτήκατε, τις μεθόδους και τις προσπάθειές τους να φέρουν τοπικά προϊόντα διατροφής πιο κοντά σας;

Πολύ χρήσιμη

Αρκετά χρήσιμη

Ουδέτερη

Όχι πολύ χρήσιμη

Καθόλου χρήσιμη

Ερώτηση #4: Βρήκατε τις δραστηριότητες που οργανώθηκαν χρήσιμες για να κατανοήσετε την αξία των τοπικών προϊόντων διατροφής και τα οφέλη τους για την υγεία σας, το περιβάλλον και την κοινωνία;

Πολύ χρήσιμες

Αρκετά χρήσιμες

Ουδέτερες

Όχι πολύ χρήσιμες

Καθόλου χρήσιμες

Ερώτηση #5: Βρήκατε αρκετές πληροφορίες σχετικά με το πώς και πού μπορείτε να βρείτε τα προϊόντα του παραγωγού/της επιχείρησης που επισκεφτήκατε;

Αρκετές και πολύ ακριβείς πληροφορίες

Αρκετές πληροφορίες αλλά χρειάζομαι περισσότερες λεπτομέρειες

Αρκετές πληροφορίες, αλλά πρέπει να ψάξω περαιτέρω μόνος μου/μόνη μου

Όχι αρκετές πληροφορίες

Καμία πληροφορία

Ερώτηση #6: Θα σκεφτόσασταν αυτή ή άλλες παρόμοιες δραστηριότητες για τον ελεύθερο χρόνο σας; Πόσο συχνά;

Μια φορά το μήνα ή συχνότερα

Τρεις με τέσσερες (3-4) φορές το χρόνο

Δύο (2) φορές το χρόνο

Μια (1) φορά το χρόνο

Ποτέ

Προτιμώ να μην απαντήσω

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

The event was co-organised by “HUB for innovation and impact” office of the American Farm School. No other strategic partners were deemed necessary for the Open Day concept. The engagement of American Farm School was presented in detail in Sections 2.2 and 2.3 of the present report.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The Open Day event was announced on social media accounts of Q-PLAN (Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter) as well as those of the American Farm School (Facebook). Additional promotion was done by professional and employee networks of both organisations.

The pre-event promotional campaign called the audience to register for the event using the online registration form. As a result of the promotional campaign, 53 adults were registered and the form was closed 2 days before the event as the maximum capacity of attendees (50 adults) was reached.

Figure 8: Event announcement on social media (Facebook, LinkedIn)

The image shows a social media post from Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL. The main graphic is orange and white, with a photo of cows on the left. The text on the graphic reads: 'AMΕΡΙΚΑΝΙΚΗ ΓΕΩΡΓΙΚΗ ΣΧΟΛΗ Θεσσαλονίκης', 'OPEN DAY', 'Επισκεφτείτε το αγρόκτημα', 'Σάββατο, 11 Μαρτίου 2023 11:00 – 14:00', 'Μαρίνου Αντύπα 54 Θέρμη Θεσσαλονίκης', and a green button that says 'ΕΓΓΡΑΦΕΙΤΕ ΤΩΡΑ'. Below the graphic, there is more text: 'Μάθετε περισσότερα για την Αμερικανική Γεωργική Σχολή www.afs.edu.gr' and 'Μάθετε περισσότερα για το έργο agroBRIDGES www.agrobridges.eu'. The social media post itself is in Greek and includes the following text: 'Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL 1,863 followers 3w • Edited •', 'Η Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL στο πλαίσιο του έργου AgroBridges Project 2021-2023, σας προσκαλεί στην εκδήλωση γνωριμίας με το αγρόκτημα της Αμερικανικής Γεωργικής Σχολής (American Farm School)', 'Σάββατο, 11 Μαρτίου 2023, ώρα 11:00 με 14:00', 'Αμερικανική Γεωργική Σχολή, Μαρίνου Αντύπα 54, Θέρμη Θεσσαλονίκης', 'Μάθετε για τις δραστηριότητες της Αμερικανικής Γεωργικής Σχολής, ξεναγηθείτε στους χώρους του αγροκτήματος & δοκιμάστε ορισμένα από τα προϊόντα του.', 'Το αγρόκτημα θα είναι ανοιχτό και μπορείτε ελεύθερα να προσκαλέσετε φίλους και οικογένεια!', 'Κάντε τώρα εγγραφή εδώ: https://lnkd.in/d/VVzWtaU', 'Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες, επικοινωνήστε εδώ: efthymiadou@qplan-intl.gr', '#openday #farmvisit #localfood #shortfoodsupplychain', 'See translation', 'You and 31 others 10 reposts', and interaction buttons for Like, Comment, Repost, and Send.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

3.1.1 Venue preparation

The organising team of the American Farm School, Q-PLAN and the caterers gathered at the premises at least one hour before the participants' arrival. Final preparations were made, including the technical set up of the auditorium, photography, placement of banners and printed material. The stand for coffee, refreshments and snacks, as well as the buffet at the restaurant area were assembled even earlier.

3.1.2 Welcome and registration of participants

Participants' arrivals started at 11.00 local time. Attendees signed the participants list and received the programme of the event, the feedback form and the agroBRIDGES leaflet. Non-registered participants signed the informed consent form to assure GDPR compliance. Following reception, people were invited to take coffee, refreshments and breakfast made with products of the American Farm School, including pies, desserts and milk.

3.1.3 Presentations

At 12.00 people were led to the auditorium of the building to attend three short presentations. At the auditorium area, the video of the ["Yes, you can!"](#) agroBRIDGES tool was playing in the background, while people were settling to attend the presentations. This video presents 12 success cases of Short Food Supply Chains across Europe.

Figure 9: Welcome and presentations

The first presentation was delivered by **Dr. Eirini Efthymiadou**, (Project Manager and agroBRIDGES Coordinator, Q-PLAN), who briefly presented the vision and objectives of agroBRIDGES, introduced the concept of SFSCs and their benefits for producers and consumers. The next speech was delivered by **Ms. Evdokia (Vicky) Krystallidou** (Director of the HUB for Innovation and Impact, AFS) who briefly talked about the history of the American Farm School and its mission, as well as the exemplary role it has played for cultivating Greek-US relations over the past 100 years. The final speech was delivered by **Dr. Konstantinos Rotsios** (Dean of Undergraduate and Graduate Studies, Perrotis College), who talked about the educational work offered by the American Farm School to students of all grades up to graduate studies (Masters' degrees).

3.1.4 Walking tour of the premises of the American Farm School

Following presentations, participants gathered at the front yard of the “Aliko Perroti” Residence and Cafeteria building to begin the tour of the premises and the educational farm. A circular route was followed leading to the most important spots of the grounds and it is illustrated in the Figure 11.

During the first part of the walking tour, Ms. **Stella Tastsidou** & Ms. **Elissavet Papadopoulou**, led the tour past educational buildings, offices, dormitories and explained their function and history, ending at the **Princeton Hall**, modelled after Princeton University in the US and constructed with the involvement of engineers from Princeton. At this spot, people stopped to rest and take photos of the viewing spot opposite the building.

Figure 10: Instances from the first part of the guided tour

Figure 11: Map of the guided tour at the premises of the American Farm School

Source: **American Farm School** (accessible at <https://afs.edu.gr/campus-map/>) – Used and adapted with permission from the owner.

The second part of the tour focused on visiting the **Educational Dairy Unit and farms**, guided by **Dr. Theodoros Kallitsis, Farm Manager of the American Farm School**. The function of the dairy unit was presented, including processes and machinery used in milk production, such as pasteurisation methods, moderation of fat content, quality control. Moreover, people were informed about a new product, called “Night’s milk” which is collected at nights. Night’s milk is an innovative product based on relevant research showing that milking at night yields melatonin-rich milk, as melatonin production in animals peaks at night. Melatonin is a substance associated with the regulation of the circadian circle (sleep) of children and the elderly; age groups most likely to suffer from insomnia. Attendees had the opportunity to see the interior of the processing unit but for safety reasons, people did not enter the manufacturing area. Then, the tour continued outdoors and strolled past the vegetable and animal farms where students produce broilers, winter and summer vegetables, legumes such as lentils and chickpeas, rice, aromatic plants, olive oil and honey, as well as fresh cut flowers. To avoid contamination of the animals by visitors and reversely, the trail followed did not pass through the farms.

Figure 12: Visitation of the Dairy Farm Unit

Figure 13: Walking past the vegetable plots and farm

The third part of the walking tour included a visit at the **campus store**, a small shop selling products produced on the educational farms, including milk, yogurt, various types of cheese, turkey, traditional pasta and wine, among other products. Visitors had the chance to buy products from the shop to try at home. The final part of the walk was unguided and led back to the restaurant area at the Residence and Cafeteria building.

Figure 14: The campus store

Figure 15: AFS products sold at the campus store

3.1.5 Lunch and food tastings

Visitors were finally received at the restaurant area for the final part of the Open Day to taste recipes made with AFS products. The lunch was a buffet that included salads, a traditional Greek spicy cheese dip, roasted vegetables, meat and vegan burgers, lasagne, grilled chicken, wine and refreshments. Cream and cocoa mousse were offered as desserts. Visitors had no limitation on servings and quantity.

Figure 16: Lunch and food tasting at the restaurant

3.2 Event participation

53 adults were registered on the online registration form, presented in Section 2.6 of the report. 17 registrants did not show up, while 5 individuals registered on the day of the event.

The event was attended by approximately 60 individuals, with team of 6 people participating as organisers, speakers, and tour guides included. 47 of the participants were adults and the rest were children. The breakdown of attendees per stakeholder category is provided in the table below, in which it can be observed that the majority of event participants were families with children.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Consumers, citizens and food enthusiasts	24
Educational institutions, teachers	6
Producers and farmers	2
Consumer associations	1
Research institutes; Researchers	1
Groups, networks and other organisations supporting agrifood businesses	4
Technology providers	1
Organising team (AFS & Q-PLAN)	6
Children (approximately)	14 - 20
Total	59 – 64

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

The results of the feedback collected at the closing of the Open Day event in Greece, are summarised in the table that follows. In total, 40 feedback forms were collected.

Question	Answers					
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	Yes		No		Not Sure	
Attendee answers	12		24		4	
Did you find the Open Day informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	Very informative	Relatively Informative	Neutral	Not Informative	Not Informative at all	
Attendee answers	23	15	2	0	0	
Did you find the activities organised helpful to meet the producer/ business / institution, their methods and their efforts to bring local food products closer to you?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	
Attendee answers	26	11	3	0	0	
Did you find the activities helpful to understand the value of local food and their benefits for your health, the environment and society?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all	
Attendee answers	28	12	0	0	0	
Did you find enough information about how and where to find the products of the farm you've visited?	Enough and very precise information	Enough information, but I would need more details	Enough information but I need to search further on my own	Not enough information	No information at all	
Attendee answers	27	10	2	1	0	
Would you consider this or other similar activities in your leisure time? How often?	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Attendee answers	12	21	7	0	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organisation?

Overall, the event was a very pleasant and informative experience for visitors, and the organising teams alike. In Greece, the concept of Open Days is mostly popular in grape and wine production, but it is important to raise awareness about other initiatives, businesses and institutions producing or promoting local food.

The activity itself is very relevant to **consumers/ citizens and their well-being**, as many people were not aware that they had the chance to get some leisure time not far from the city. Moreover, Open Days can play an important role in **awareness raising and promotion of local food**, as the promotion and branding of local food is heavily based on memory and experiences. Open Days offer an immersive experience and create positive associations with food for consumers.

Local small-scale producers, businesses and educational institutions like the American Farm School, work very hard to produce quality food and create tangible impact, taking pride on their efforts. So, such events **can be extremely motivating** for producers, especially when people get to know them, their activities and products at their own site.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes. Such events are highly recommended and can strengthen local SFSCs if organised on a frequent basis, so that consumers know how to anticipate them. In Greece, the concept worked perfectly, given that the event concept had to be tailored to the history, activities and products of the American Farm School. According to collected feedback, most people would like to see Open Days happen 3-4 times a year or more frequently.

If the event was organized again in the region, more information would be provided to guests about available sales points in the local market or online, to buy the products of the visited farm. This information would be handed over in the form of a printed / online brochure containing also some facts and a brief history of the visited location. This was supported by 37.5% of the event participants stating that they would still need further research to find the products of AFS following the event.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organisation needs?

The “Let’s meet!” event organisation guidelines convey the needs of the Open Day concept quite effectively. Some processes could be explained in more detail; for instance, the registration process and some tips about the collection / processing / publication of personal data, photos and videos in a GDPR-compliant manner could be provided.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

The guidelines provided high-level instructions on the organisation of open days, with planning activities and effort being explained with high accuracy, but not to the point where flexibility in event planning is sacrificed. Some useful examples, tips and more accurate estimations could be added, taking advantage of the experience the agroBRIDGES consortium gained from organising the “Let’s meet!” events.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the guidelines are flexible, accommodating similar events in diverse contexts, such as location, agri-food product categories and different business models of production.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

As a mostly outdoor activity, the “Open Day” concept can be affected by weather conditions on the day of the event. Such guidelines of course cannot be provided to organisers. A recommendation would be to carefully consider seasonality of products, accessibility of the farm location and extreme weather phenomena and try to schedule the Open Day, when the conditions are expected to be optimal.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

For the concept, no suggestions for improvement can be offered, as it worked very well. The participants’ list needs to be enriched and include more information about the participants, such as signatures, number of children, or other demographics (age groups, gender). The “organization name” field is redundant for this type of event, as it targets people mostly in their role as consumers/citizens.

Guidelines could be more informative for organisers on how to collect and use personal data, in line with the GDPR, as it is unlikely that small-scale farmers have sufficient knowledge on the matter.

5. Conclusions

The organisation of the Open Day event in Greece was perceived to be particularly successful by the organising teams of Q-PLAN and of the American Farm School, as well as by the event participants. The organisation of similar events **at regional level** and **on a systematic basis**, can be a powerful tool for raising awareness about locally produced food and to promote consumer – producer interactions for promoting Short Food Supply Chains. Such events can equally accommodate the needs of consumers visiting an open farm for **recreation** and for **education/ awareness** about the stories of the products and the farmers. The event is suitable for families with children and food enthusiasts. If combined with information about the available sales channels of products, the event could create a long-lasting impact for producers / farmers as well.